

Questionnaire items

Respond to the following statements according to your experience with recent open-book exams (requiring digital product).

1: Strongly Disagree; 2: Disagree; 3: Agree; 4: Strongly Agree; 5: NS/NC

1. The time to take the exam (2 hours) was about right.
2. The type of exam required the student to come in person to take the exam.
3. The type of exam was in line with the pedagogy/methodology.
4. The type of exam promoted more complex learning (creating, reflecting, etc.) and less rote learning.
5. The type of exam is intellectually challenging.
6. The type of exam is better suited to the learning style of each student.
7. The type of exam is more related to professional practice.
8. The content of the exam was attractive.
9. The type of exam allowed cheating (plagiarism, copying, etc.).

Respond to the following statements according to your experience in the previous face-to-face exams.

1: Strongly Disagree; 2: Disagree; 3: Agree; 4: Strongly Agree; 5: NS/NC

1. The time to take the exam (2 hours) was about right.
2. The type of exam required the student to come in person to take the exam.
3. The type of exam was in line with the pedagogy/methodology.
4. The type of exam promoted more complex learning (creating, reflecting, etc.) and less rote learning.
5. The type of exam is intellectually challenging.
6. The type of exam is better suited to the learning style of each student.
7. The type of exam is more related to professional practice.
8. The content of the exam was attractive.
9. The type of exam allowed cheating (plagiarism, copying, etc.).

Reference:

Williams, J. B. & Wong, A. (2009). The efficacy of final examinations: A comparative study of closed-book, invigilated exams and open-book, open-web exams. *British Journal of Educational Technology*, 40, 2, 227–236.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-8535.2008.00929.x>